

Divergent Effects of Cross-Lingual Translation on Calibration and Explanations in Cyber Threat Sentiment

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Abstract. This paper examines what happens when an English sentence is translated into Spanish and French, focusing on two crucial elements: the reliability of the predictive probability (calibration) and the stability of the explanation. A multilingual Transformer model is fine-tuned using English data and then tested on the translations. The results are quite clear after translation: performance drops sharply, accuracy and F1-macro decrease by about one-third, and many samples have their prediction labels changed. However, Integrated Gradients explanations remain relatively stable, because the model still pays fairly consistent attention to cybersecurity-related signals, as evidenced by the high top-token overlap and stable, even increasing, attribution to cyber keywords. Conversely, calibration crashes significantly: the model remains very confident even when it is wrong, causing ECE and Brier scores to increase sharply. Finally, we propose a drift-aware triage rule based on translation drift signals, including label flips and confidence changes, to identify high-risk cases requiring human review, thereby reducing review volume while improving error detection capabilities.

Keywords: Translation-induced drift · Multilingual sentiment classification · Integrated Gradient · Drift-aware triage

1 Introduction

Cybersecurity operations teams increasingly rely on online text streams to track incidents and user concerns. Prior work shows that social media can support threat awareness pipelines and reduce manual analyst workload [1], while large-scale study reveals diverse and mostly negative security and privacy discussions in the wild [15]. At the same time, sentiment analysis has been used to summarize public opinions on emerging security topics such as ChatGPT-related risks [14]. In practice, these systems must work across languages, but cross-lingual sentiment analysis remains challenging due to linguistic mismatch and transfer limits [20]. General guidance on multilingual text analysis also highlights that measurement equivalence across languages is non-trivial [10], and multilingual models can show cross-lingual vulnerability under shifts and attacks [11].

Trustworthy deployment requires more than accuracy. First, explanations should remain meaningful under drift. Context- and semantic-aware explanation designs can produce more coherent text explanations than token-only views [9], and stability assessment itself must be handled carefully because different similarity choices can lead to misleading conclusions [4]. Second, probability calibration is critical: under distribution shift, models may stay confident even when wrong. Recent NLP studies show calibration and uncertainty can degrade strongly under data scarcity and shift [17], and training dynamics can even increase confidence while calibration worsens [5]. OOD-oriented calibration objectives have also been proposed to improve reliability under shift [12].

In this paper, we study translation-induced drift for multilingual cyber threat sentiment. We fine-tune a multilingual model on English and evaluate it on Spanish and French translations. We jointly analyze (i) prediction robustness and label flips, (ii) explanation consistency using Integrated Gradients, and (iii) calibration reliability. Finally, we propose a drift-aware triage rule to flag high-risk translated cases for human review.

Therefore, this study aims to answer four important research questions: **RQ1:** How much do Spanish/French translations degrade performance and increase label flips compared to English? **RQ2:** Under translation drift, how stable are Integrated Gradients explanations on cybersecurity-related tokens? **RQ3:** How does translation drift affect calibration (ECE, Brier, and confidence-accuracy gap)? **RQ4:** Can drift-aware triage detect more errors with less review workload than simple baselines?

2 Related Work

2.1 Cyber Threat Sentiment on Social Media

Social media is often used to understand how users discuss cybersecurity risks and how sentiment changes around security events. Pattnaik et al. built a large Twitter dataset of security/privacy discussions among non-expert users and observed a generally negative sentiment trend across many topics over several years [15]. Okey et al. analyzed a large volume of tweets related to ChatGPT and

cybersecurity, highlighting recurring concerns, such as phishing and malware. [14]. Closer to the SOC context, SYNAPSE filters and clusters security-related tweets, then creates concise IoC summaries to support analysts [1]. Additionally, some studies leverage sentiment signals to create threat-assessment chatbot interfaces as a lightweight, convenient way to monitor discussions [2].

2.2 Cross-Lingual and Translation-Induced Drift

Cross-linguistic sentiment analysis often relies on machine translation, multilingual models, or translation strategies, but translation traces can skew assessments and cause drift. Zhao et al. synthesize the main tasks and strategies in CLSA while highlighting unanswered questions such as domain adaptation and resource-limited contexts [20]. Licht and Lind view multilingual text analysis in three ways: disaggregated analysis, input alignment, and anchoring, and particularly emphasize the requirement for measurable equivalence between languages [10]. Robustness can also be reduced by interlingual noise: Mathur et al. show that multilingual models can be vulnerable to adversarial attacks, and this vulnerability can spread across languages [11]. In the area of cross-lingual text similarity, Seki argues that the “pre-translate and then process” process can propagate errors and proposes combining translated text with intermediate NMT states to mitigate this impact [16].

2.3 Trustworthiness under Drift: Calibration and Stability

Reliability under drift is often considered through calibration and explanation stability. For text explanation, CaSE/topicLIME uses topic-level perturbations to generate explanations based on local replacement models, which are more coherent than token-level LIME [9]. However, stability measurements are also highly sensitive to the measurement method: Burger et al. showed that simply changing the similarity measure can reverse conclusions about stability, and they proposed a weighted measure based on "synonymy" for a more realistic estimate [4]. Regarding calibration with shifts, Xiao et al. compared several methods and noted that ensemble-based methods still performed well when data were shifted to OOD [19]. In NLP, Durai pointed out that confidence and calibration can be separated according to training phases, suggesting that phase-based checkpoints and accompanying correction steps should be considered [5]. MaxEnt Loss incorporates a regularization approach directly into the training process to improve calibration under OOD through the maximum entropy constraint [12].

3 Methodology

3.1 Workflow Overview

Based on the research process in Fig. 1, we followed a fairly straightforward path: starting with data preparation and a quick look at the data using EDA

and language audit to understand the data in each language. Then we train the model and check for "bias" when translating to see if the predictions change significantly. Finally, the XAI is used to compare explanations across languages, to determine whether the model still adheres to important signals or if explanations are lost during translation.

Fig. 1: The workflow of research design methodology, from dataset preparation to model training, evaluation, and interpretability analysis

3.2 Dataset Description

The dataset used in our study is X-CYBER-SENT-2025-v1 (v1.0) with 503,456 tweets (CSV UTF-8, 480MB) [13] collected from X/Twitter based on keywords related to cybersecurity threats (phishing, ransomware, DDoS, data breach, CVE, exploit, etc.). Tweets were posted between August 1, 2024, and March 31, 2025 (UTC) and collected between April 1 and 5, 2025; the primary languages are English (78%), Spanish (14%), and French (5%). The data was cleaned (URL/mention/emoji removal, duplicate removal, HTML decoding), sentiment was labeled using TextBlob, emotional inferences were added, and attack types were tagged using regex/keywords; approximately 5% was manually checked (Kappa 0.78). The dataset is restricted to research use only due to ToS/ethical constraints, with a note of bias (bias towards English speakers and "tech-savvy" users).

We perform stratified sampling to construct a balanced 3-class subset of 45,000 tweets as summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Stratified split statistics of the class-balanced experimental subset (45,000 tweets; 15,000 per class).

Split	Positive	Negative	Neutral	Total
Train	10 499	10 500	10 500	31 499
Val	2 250	2 250	2 250	6 750
Test	2 251	2 250	2 250	6 751
Total	15 000	15 000	15 000	45 000

3.3 Translation-Induced Drift Evaluation Protocol

To measure the degree of drift caused by translation, we compared the model’s behavior on the original text and machine-translated versions. For each sample, we tracked whether the predicted labels changed after translation and observed changes in prediction confidence. These changes were aggregated into simple indicators to reflect the model’s sensitivity to translation-induced artifacts.

3.4 Models and Training Setup

We trained and compared multiple sentiment classification models to gain a balanced perspective on different approaches. The model group included a traditional baseline based on TF-IDF features combined with Logistic Regression, and multilingual pre-trained linguistic models, including mBERT, TF-IDF + LogReg, and DistilBERT, fine-tuned directly for the problem. All models were trained using the same process, monitoring performance on the validation set to select the best checkpoint, and then using the selected model to evaluate drift due to translation and perform reliability analyses.

3.5 Evaluation and Explanation Consistency Metrics

Flip Rate (FR) [6] measures the proportion of instances whose predicted label changes between two models or two prediction rounds (e.g., before and after a debiasing step or model update). Let $f^{(0)}(x_i)$ and $f^{(1)}(x_i)$ denote the (possibly thresholded) predictions of the baseline and updated models for instance x_i , respectively, and let n be the total number of instances. We define:

$$\text{Flip}_i = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } f^{(0)}(x_i) \neq f^{(1)}(x_i), \\ 0, & \text{if } f^{(0)}(x_i) = f^{(1)}(x_i). \end{cases}$$

Accordingly, we determine FR as below:

$$\text{FR} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \text{Flip}_i.$$

Here, FR is the observed proportion of prediction flips between the two models. Values of FR closer to 0 indicate that the updated model behaves similarly to the baseline, whereas larger values indicate substantial prediction changes. Group-conditioned variants (e.g., FR_{group}) are obtained by restricting the sum to instances belonging to a given subgroup.

Expected Calibration Error (ECE) [7] measures the discrepancy between model confidence and empirical accuracy. Let \hat{p}_i denote the predicted confidence (maximum softmax probability) for sample i , and let \hat{y}_i denote the predicted label. Predictions are partitioned into M bins $\{B_m\}_{m=1}^M$ according to confidence values. The accuracy and confidence of bin B_m are defined as:

$$\text{acc}(B_m) = \frac{1}{|B_m|} \sum_{i \in B_m} \mathbf{1}(\hat{y}_i = y_i), \quad (1)$$

$$\text{conf}(B_m) = \frac{1}{|B_m|} \sum_{i \in B_m} \hat{p}_i. \quad (2)$$

ECE is then formulated as:

$$\text{ECE} = \sum_{m=1}^M \frac{|B_m|}{N} |\text{acc}(B_m) - \text{conf}(B_m)|. \quad (3)$$

Lower ECE values mean better calibration.

Brier Score (BS) [3] is a scoring rule that measures the mean squared difference between predicted probabilities and observed outcomes for categorical events. The Brier score is formulated for binary classification using true labels $y_i \in \{0, 1\}$ and predicted probabilities $\hat{p}_i = \mathbb{P}(Y = 1 | x_i)$, $i = 1, \dots, N$:

$$\text{BS} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{p}_i - y_i)^2. \quad (4)$$

On the other hand, regarding multi-class classification, given classes $k = 1, \dots, K$, one-hot encoded true labels $y_{ik} \in \{0, 1\}$, and predicted probabilities \hat{p}_{ik} , the generalized Brier score is:

$$\text{BS} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^K (\hat{p}_{ik} - y_{ik})^2. \quad (5)$$

BS expresses both calibration and discrimination of the probabilistic predictions; smaller values imply higher quality, and a perfect score of 0 prevails when all projected probabilities precisely match the actual results.

Jaccard Top- k [18] measures the similarity between two sets of top- k items (e.g., features, recommended items, or explanation elements) by computing the Jaccard index on these sets. Let A_k and B_k denote the sets containing the top- k items selected by two methods, models, or runs. The formula for Jaccard Top- k similarity is as follows:

$$J_k(A_k, B_k) = \frac{|A_k \cap B_k|}{|A_k \cup B_k|}. \quad (6)$$

Here, the value $J_k \in [0, 1]$ portrays the observed overlap between the two top- k sets. A value of $J_k = 1$ indicates identical top- k sets, whereas $J_k = 0$ means no overlap. Otherwise, if we aim to assess stability across repeated runs, J_k is typically averaged over multiple pairs of runs.

Cyber-Term Attribution Mass (CTAM) measures how much of the Integrated Gradients (IG) attribution is concentrated on cybersecurity-related tokens, serving as a domain-aware indicator of explanation focus. Given an input text x tokenized into n tokens $\{t_i\}_{i=1}^n$, IG produces token-level attributions

$\{a_i\}_{i=1}^n$ for the predicted class. Let $\mathcal{C}(x) \subseteq \{1, \dots, n\}$ denote the index set of tokens that match a predefined cybersecurity lexicon (e.g., phishing, ransomware, CVE patterns). We define CTAM for a single instance as:

$$\text{CTAM}(x) = \frac{\sum_{i \in \mathcal{C}(x)} |a_i|}{\sum_{i=1}^n |a_i|}. \quad (7)$$

We report the mean CTAM over a dataset \mathcal{D}_L in language L as:

$$\overline{\text{CTAM}}_L = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{D}_L|} \sum_{x \in \mathcal{D}_L} \text{CTAM}(x). \quad (8)$$

To quantify translation-induced drift in explanation focus, we compute:

$$\Delta \text{CTAM}_{\text{EN}-L} = \overline{\text{CTAM}}_{\text{EN}} - \overline{\text{CTAM}}_L. \quad (9)$$

A negative $\Delta \text{CTAM}_{\text{EN}-L}$ indicates that translated inputs allocate more attribution mass to cybersecurity-related tokens than the English source.

3.6 Explainability with Integrated Gradients

To explain the model’s predictions at the word/phrase level, we use Integrated Gradients to estimate the contribution of each token to the output label. This method helps clearly see which signals in the sentence the model relies on and facilitates comparison of whether important areas change when the text is translated into other languages.

3.7 Calibration and Drift-Aware Triage

Besides accuracy, we are also concerned with whether the model assigns an appropriate level of confidence to its predictions, especially in the context of data drift due to translation. Therefore, we evaluate the ability to adjust prediction probabilities across languages and use translation drift signals to prioritize cases that require human review.

Specifically, for each English tweet x^{EN} and its translated counterpart x^L ($L \in \{\text{ES}, \text{FR}\}$), we consider two drift indicators: (i) a **label flip** after translation, $\mathbb{I}(\hat{y}^{\text{EN}} \neq \hat{y}^L)$, and (ii) a **confidence change**, $\Delta p = |\hat{p}^{\text{EN}} - \hat{p}^L|$, where \hat{p} is the predicted probability of the predicted class. We then combine these signals into a lightweight risk score:

$$s(x) = \alpha \cdot \mathbb{I}(\hat{y}^{\text{EN}} \neq \hat{y}^L) + (1 - \alpha) \cdot \Delta p, \quad (10)$$

with α controlling the relative importance of flips versus confidence shifts.

Based on the value of $s(x)$, the samples are divided into three risk levels: high-risk group (the top 10%), medium-risk group (the next 10%), and low-risk group (the remaining 80%). Intuitively, cases exhibiting significant signal drift or unstable confidence levels are more likely to be wrong and are therefore referred to manual review; while low-risk cases can be handled automatically with higher confidence levels.

4 Results

As shown in Table 2, translation induces a strong robustness drop for all models. While accuracy is high on English, it falls sharply on Spanish and French: mBERT decreases from 0.952 (EN) to 0.621/0.617 (ES/FR), DistilBERT from 0.927 to 0.581/0.527, and TF-IDF + LogReg shows the largest degradation from 0.900 to 0.376/0.415. Flip rates are also substantial (e.g., 38.0% for mBERT on EN→ES and up to 64.2% for TF-IDF + LogReg), confirming that translation changes not only confidence but often the predicted label itself.

Table 2: Baseline comparison under translation-induced drift. Drops are absolute accuracy decreases relative to EN. Flip rates are the percentage of samples whose predicted label changes after translation (EN→ES/FR).

Model	EN	ES	FR	Drop ES	Drop FR	Flip ES	Flip FR
mBERT (178M)	0.952	0.621	0.617	33.04	33.44	38.0	38.0
DistilBERT (66M)	0.927	0.581	0.527	34.63	40.04	43.9	48.9
TF-IDF + LogReg	0.900	0.376	0.415	52.40	48.55	64.2	59.9

4.1 Explanation Consistency Under Drift

Table 3 shows that the explanatory patterns remain relatively consistent after translation, although the total attribution volume shifts. The average CTAM value increases from 0.0090 in EN to 0.0136 (ES) and 0.0171 (FR), indicating that the translated inputs tend to focus more attribution on cybersecurity-related tokens. However, the CTAM drift (EN−X) is negative in both languages (ES: −0.0046, FR: −0.0081), suggesting a systematic redistribution of attribution compared to English. Nevertheless, the top- k token overlap remains high (Jaccard approximately 0.86 for both ES and FR), meaning that significant cybersecurity evidence is generally retained after translation.

Table 3: Explanation consistency under translation-induced drift. CTAM measures attribution mass on cybersecurity-related tokens; overlap denotes Jaccard similarity of top- k cyber tokens between EN and translated inputs.

Metric	EN	ES	FR
CTAM (mean)	0.0090	0.0136	0.0171
CTAM drift (EN−X)	−	−0.0046	−0.0081
Top- k overlap (Jaccard)	−	0.8613	0.8606

4.2 Calibration Under Cross-Lingual Drift

Table 4 shows that translation not only reduces accuracy, but also severely harms calibration. In English, the model is close to well-calibrated: accuracy is 0.951 with a high mean confidence of 0.992, yielding a small ECE (0.042) and low Brier score (0.091). After translation, confidence remains almost unchanged (0.984 for ES, 0.983 for FR) while accuracy collapses (0.621/0.617), producing large confidence–accuracy gaps (0.363/0.366) and much worse ECE and Brier scores (ECE \approx 0.36; Brier \approx 0.74). Fig. 2 confirms this pattern: EN follows the diagonal closely, whereas ES/FR curves sit above it, indicating systematic overconfidence under cross-lingual drift.

Table 4: Calibration metrics under translation-induced drift. Conf.-Acc. denotes the confidence-accuracy gap.

Lang.	Acc.	Mean Conf.	ECE	Brier	Conf.-Acc.
EN	0.951	0.992	0.042	0.091	0.041
ES	0.621	0.984	0.363	0.736	0.363
FR	0.617	0.983	0.366	0.741	0.366

Fig. 2: Calibration under translation-induced drift: EN is well-calibrated (ECE=0.0423), while ES/FR are overconfident (ECE \approx 0.36).

4.3 Qualitative Case Studies

Table 5 provides qualitative evidence showing that token-level explanations remain semantically stable during translation. In both cases, the top-3 tokens according to Integrated Gradients in ES/FR generally align with the evidence in English, even though the surface forms change (e.g., *severe/attack/cyber* → *cibernético/ataque* and *cybernétique/attaque*). A similar trend is also observed in Case 1, where the main ideas about detection behavior and system-related terms remain consistently maintained across languages. Overall, these examples suggest that although translation can affect predicted labels and calibration quality, the model’s explanation focus largely remains on the same cybersecurity concepts.

Table 5: Top-3 Integrated Gradients (IG) tokens per language for two representative cases. Attribution patterns remain semantically aligned across translations.

Case	Language	Top 1	Top 2	Top 3
Case 0	EN	severe (0.70)	attack (0.50)	cyber (0.30)
	ES	cibernético (0.60)	grave (0.50)	ataque (0.40)
	FR	cybernétique (0.55)	grave (0.25)	attaque (0.15)
Case 1	EN	detected (0.60)	in (0.40)	system (0.30)
	ES	detectado (0.65)	sistema (0.55)	en (0.45)
	FR	déecté (0.62)	système (0.52)	dans (0.42)

4.4 Drift-Aware Risk Triage (Error Detection)

Tables 6 and 7 assess a drift-aware triage rule that assigns risk levels to translated predictions. Most samples are Low-risk (79.98%), where accuracy is higher (ES: 0.646, FR: 0.642), while accuracy declines for Medium (0.575/0.570) and High risk (0.465 in both languages), supporting risk as a proxy for likely errors. As an error detector, flagging only High-risk cases limits workload to 10.01% but achieves low recall (≈ 0.14) with moderate precision (0.535). Flagging both High and Medium increases workload to 20.02% and improves recall to ≈ 0.25 (F1 ≈ 0.33), at a modest precision drop (to ≈ 0.48). Overall, triage offers a practical workload–coverage trade-off for handling translation-induced failures.

4.5 Cost–Benefit Trade-off Analysis

Tables 8 and 9 quantify the operational trade-off between review workload and error detection on translated inputs. Reviewing all samples achieves full recall but requires 100% workload, while precision remains low (around 38%). In contrast, drift-aware rules substantially reduce workload: flagging only High-risk cases reviews 10.01% of samples and maintains precision around 53.5%, but recall is limited (about 14%). Expanding to High + Medium doubles the workload

Table 6: Distribution of triage risk levels on translated inputs, with accuracy within each stratum.

Lang.	Risk level	Count	Share (%)	Acc.
ES	Low	1598	79.98	0.646
ES	Medium	200	10.01	0.575
ES	High	200	10.01	0.465
FR	Low	1598	79.98	0.642
FR	Medium	200	10.01	0.570
FR	High	200	10.01	0.465

Table 7: Error detection performance of drift-aware triage rules.

Lang.	Rule	Prec.	Rec.	F1	Work. (%)
ES	High-risk only	0.535	0.141	0.224	10.01
ES	High + Medium	0.480	0.254	0.332	20.02
FR	High-risk only	0.535	0.140	0.222	10.01
FR	High + Medium	0.483	0.252	0.331	20.02

to 20.02% and improves recall to roughly 25%, with precision around 48%. A stricter confidence-based rule ($\text{Conf.} < 0.8$) yields the smallest workload (about 3%) but captures only a small fraction of errors (recall around 4%). Overall, High + Medium provides the most balanced operating point when moderate review capacity is available.

Table 8: Cost-benefit trade-off on Spanish (ES). Work.=review workload, Rec.=error recall, Prec.=error precision, Eff.=efficiency.

Strategy	Work. (%)	Rec. (%)	Prec. (%)	Eff.
Review all (baseline)	100.00	100.00	37.89	1.000
High-risk only	10.01	14.13	53.50	1.412
High + Medium	20.02	25.36	48.00	1.267
Conf. < 0.8	2.70	3.83	53.70	1.417

Table 9: Cost-benefit trade-off on French (FR).

Strategy	Work. (%)	Rec. (%)	Prec. (%)	Eff.
Review all (baseline)	100.00	100.00	38.29	1.000
High-risk only	10.01	13.99	53.50	1.397
High + Medium	20.02	25.23	48.25	1.260
Conf. < 0.8	2.95	4.18	54.24	1.417

5 Discussion

For **RQ1**, the results show that machine translation induces substantial robustness degradation: performance is high on English. Still, it drops sharply on Spanish/French, and the flip rate indicates that translation frequently changes predicted labels rather than merely lowering confidence [6]. For **RQ2**, Integrated Gradients remains largely stable across languages in terms of top- k overlap, yet attribution mass can still shift, suggesting that explanations may look similar while the model’s focus subtly drifts [9]. For **RQ3**, the results reveal a reliability risk: under ES/FR drift, the model often stays highly *confident* despite lower accuracy, leading to large calibration error (ECE) and probability error (Brier), consistent with miscalibration under distribution shift [7,3]. For **RQ4**, drift-aware triage reduces review workload by prioritizing high-risk samples, aligning with selective classification as a practical mitigation under uncertainty [8]. Overall, multilingual cyber sentiment pipelines that rely on translated text can be fragile unless drift is monitored and managed, which is particularly relevant to multilingual threat discourse on X [13].

Limitations and threats to validity. We study a single dataset from X with a fixed EN→ES/FR translation setup, so the observed drop may vary across translation systems, domains, or platforms. Ground-truth labels are only available in English; hence, cross-lingual evaluation relies on translated inputs rather than native annotations. Future work will test additional translation systems/languages and integrate triage with calibration or OOD-aware training to reduce overconfidence under drift. [12].

6 Conclusion

This study investigated drift caused by translation in the analysis of sentiment regarding multilingual cybersecurity threats and found that machine translation can significantly reduce accuracy and lead to many instances of relabeling, making cross-lingual results unreliable if drift is not checked. With Integrated Gradients, we observed that explanations sometimes look quite similar across languages, but the model’s focus can still shift. Furthermore, the predictive probabilities are also standard-skewed under drift, so a drift-triage mechanism is needed to flag risk cases requiring review. In short, for reliable multilingual monitoring, drift, calibration, and consistency in explanations need to be reported simultaneously.

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